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**Antiarrhythmic Treatment by Amiodaron:
Present State and Future**

M.D. THESIS

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Abstract

Cardiac arrhythmias are one of the most common disorders affecting people today. Various medications and surgical interventions are used to manage and treat cardiac arrhythmias. Among these cardiac arrhythmias is atrial fibrillation (AF) one of the most common. The cardiac conduction system uses electrical impulses to control the speed and rhythm of each heartbeat. Normally, each heartbeat starts in the right atrium in the sinoatrial (SA) node. Action potentials generated by the SA node's pacemaker cells spread to the walls of the atria and cause their contraction and continue to the atrioventricular (AV) node. AF is a form of supraventricular tachyarrhythmia, which is characterized by uncoordinated atrial activation that leads to a decline in the mechanical function of the atria in the heart. AF is the most common rhythm disturbance in adults. It can be paroxysmal, persistent or permanent. The first registration of AF was recorded by Willem Einthoven in 1906 with his development of electrocardiography. AF affects about 4.5-6 million people in Europe, about 6 million in China and more than 2 million in the USA. More than 60 percent of these patients have symptoms. Most severe complications caused by AF are stroke and thromboembolism. Antiarrhythmic agents are classified by the Vaughan Williams classification according to their effect on the cardio myocyte AP. Among these is the drug amiodarone. Amiodarone is a class III antiarrhythmic agent that expresses its efficacy on all the phases of the action potential. Thus, it became very popular to treat arrhythmic patients with amiodarone. Amiodarone is extracted from khellin – an extract from the *Ammi visnaga* plant found in Afrika. It was when the Argentinian physician Mauricio Rosenbaum started to use amiodarone to treat his patients with supraventricular and ventricular arrhythmias that the popularity of amiodarone started to expand. Amiodarone is an iodinated benzofurane (highly liposoluble) derivative. Its chemical formula is $C_{25}H_{29}I_2NO_3$. It is a highly iodine rich compound. It can seep into all tissues but is found highly in adipose tissue. The lipophilicity of amiodarone is one of the main reasons it can cause vast side effects. Amiodarone side effects are ocular, dermatological, hepatic, pulmonic and thymotic to name but a few. Due to this fact it has been a priority of many pharmacist and doctors to discover a new drug with fewer side effects, but which have the same or similar efficacy as amiodarone. These drugs are dronedarone and vernakalant. Dronedarone is a derivative of amiodarone but does not contain iodine. These drugs are effective and classed as class III drugs like amiodarone, but though their side effect are less they do not show as good efficacy as amiodarone. With better tools and better knowhow of surgical and ICD devices, cardiac pathologies such as AF can be treated quite well. However, amiodarone's role in modern medicine is still of utmost importance to further treat and manage the whole spectrum of arrhythmias where other drugs show less efficacy of treating such pathologies.

Abbreviations

ACh - acetylcholine
ACLS - advanced cardiac life support
AERP - atrial effective refractory period
Afib - atrial fibrillation
AF - atrial fibrillation
AIH – amiodarone induced hypothyroidism
AIT – amiodarone induced thyroid toxicity
APB – atrial premature beat
APD - action potential duration
AV - atrioventricular node
BNP - brain natriuretic peptide
Ca²⁺ - calcium ion
cAMP - cyclic adenosine monophosphate
CPR - cardiopulmonary resuscitation
CRP - C reactive protein
CV - conduction velocity
ICD - Implantable Cardiofibrillator
INR - international normalized ratio
I_f - funny channel
K⁺ - potassium ion
Na⁺ - sodium ion
NOAC - new oral anticoagulant
ROSC - return of spontaneous circulation
SA - sinoatrial node
SCA – sudden cardiac arrest
TDM = Therapeutic Drug Monitoring

Introduction

Within the field of medicine, the definition of arrhythmia is that heartbeats may be too slow (*bradycardia = less than 60 beats per minute*), too rapid (*tachycardia = greater than 100 beats per minute*), too irregular (*fibrillations*), or too early (*premature contraction*). Cardiac arrhythmias are one of the most common disorders or illnesses affecting people today. Various drugs, medications and surgical interventions are used to manage and treat cardiac arrhythmias.

In this thesis, the aetiology, epidemiology, signs and symptoms of arrhythmias will be briefly explained as well as the classifications of various anti-arrhythmic medications and their classes. The main emphasis, however, is going to be on the drug amiodarone and Class III of antiarrhythmic drugs, the pharmacokinetics of amiodarone and its function, and the future of amiodarone. Amiodarone has multiple actions. Besides blocking K^+ channels, amiodarone also blocks Na^+ channels, Ca^{2+} channels and even some α - and β -receptors.

The main purpose of this thesis is to make it easier for future medical doctors to understand the main function of amiodarone, its usage, its benefits, its functions as a clinical diagnostic tool, its therapeutic monitoring, and its side effects.

Cardiac Rhythm and its Action Potential

The cardiac conduction system uses electrical impulses to control the speed and rhythm of each heartbeat. Normally, each heartbeat starts in the right atrium in the sinoatrial (SA) node. Action potentials generated by the SA node's pacemaker cells spread to the walls of the atria and cause their contraction and continue to the atrioventricular (AV) node. After a delay, the electrical signal diverges and is conducted through the left and right bundle of His to the respective Purkinje-fibres for each side of the heart, leading to the contraction of the ventricles. This is a continuous loop and is repeated with each heartbeat. The SA node is not, however, the only region of the heart capable of cyclically generating action potentials; it is merely the dominant one that overrides the others. The AV node and the bundle of His are also capable of automaticity when it is not driven by the SA node.

Figure 1: Comparison of the ionic currents underlying SA node and ventricular myocyte action potentials. The constant leak of Na^+ from SA node pacemaker cells leads to a continuously depolarising baseline. This ultimately opens voltage gated ion channels leading to an action potential. In ventricular myocytes, the membrane potential is stable until the depolarising stimulus arrives, again causing voltage gated ion channels to open. Note that the ionic currents underlying the action potential in each case are different: Ca^{2+} for SA node cells and Na^+ for ventricular cells (Vander et al., 2001).

In the *pacemaker cells*, the resting membrane potential is negative. An action potential begins with the voltage becoming more positive. In this, a non-specific cation channel (I_f = funny channel) has the most important role. It is a voltage-dependent ion channel, which opens during

membrane hyperpolarisation. Through this, Na^+ leaks into the cells slowly. This slow depolarising baseline drift is the key to automaticity (spontaneous diastolic depolarisation). After this, two sets of voltage gated Ca^{2+} channels contribute to the upstroke of the action potential. The first channel to come into play is the T-type Ca^{2+} channel, which opens at a specific level of membrane depolarisation. These open transiently (thus T-type), providing the initial depolarising kick to fire the action potential proper, which is mediated by the opening of L-type (L for long-lasting) Ca^{2+} channels. After a brief delay, the L-type calcium channels close and the voltage gated K^+ channels open. The increased K^+ current that follows in response will drive membrane potential back down again. This hyperpolarisation opens the Na^+ leak channels, thus starting the process again (Vander et al., 2001, pp. 390-406).

The action potential in *ventricular myocytes* differs from the SA nodal action potential. Ventricular myocytes have no capacity for generating action potentials, and their resting membrane potential rests at a stable level until an action potential arrives from the bundle of His. Fast Na^+ channels open, rapidly depolarising the cell (Phase 0). This initiates the ventricular action potential, which is followed by an early repolarisation phase (Phase 1), because of the opening of the early, transient K^+ channels. At this point, voltage gated L-type Ca^{2+} channels open and an increase in Ca^{2+} entry and contraction of the myocyte occur (Phase 2 - Plato phase). When these calcium channels close and the late, rapid K^+ channels open, the membrane potential decreases. It is called repolarisation (Phase 3), and it brings the membrane potential back to its resting level (Phase 4). As in skeletal muscles, there is a refractory period during which ventricular myocytes cannot sustain an action potential due to the inactivation of Na^+ channels.

Regulation by the autonomic nervous system

The sympathetic nervous system increase heart rate (positive chronotropy) by decreasing the time to produce an action potential in the SA node. It also increases the conduction velocity and the power of the muscle contractions. A hormone called noradrenaline is released, which binds to, and activates, receptors on the pacemaker cell membrane known as β_1 adrenoceptors. This activates a protein called a G_s -protein (s for stimulatory). Activation of the G-protein leads to increased levels of cAMP in the cell (via the cAMP pathway). cAMP binds to the so-called funny channels, increasing the sodium current and therefore increasing the rate of depolarization during the pacemaker potential. The increased cAMP also increases the opening time of L-type calcium channels, increasing the Ca^{2+} current through the channel.

The parasympathetic nervous system decreases heart rate (negative chronotropy) by increasing the time taken to produce an action potential in the SA node. The Vagus nerve travels to the sinoatrial node, releases a molecule called acetylcholine (ACh), which binds to a receptor located on the outside of the pacemaker cell, called an M2 muscarinic receptor. This activates a G_i-protein (I for inhibitory) which activates a special set of potassium channels, increasing potassium flow out of the cell and decreasing membrane potential, meaning that the pacemaker cells take longer to reach their threshold value. The G_i-protein also inhibits the cAMP pathway and inhibits funny channels and L-type calcium channels.

These are important details when it comes to the complex mechanism of amiodarone. Amiodarone inhibits K⁺ channels, which results in slower repolarization of the cells. It also inhibits Na⁺ channels when the heart rate is elevated and causes slower depolarization and conduction velocity in a frequency-dependent manner. L-type Ca²⁺ channels are also inhibited, and with chronic use of amiodarone, inhibition of α- and β- adrenergic receptors is detected because of down-regulation of these receptors. This explains why amiodarone is an effective drug in a wide range of conditions when the normal heart rhythm is disturbed.

Arrhythmias

Disturbances within the physiological cardiac conduction pathway cause the heart to have an abnormal rhythm called an arrhythmia. Arrhythmias may be classified by rate, mechanism, duration and the site of origin. The following classification of subtypes of arrhythmias is summarized from *Herold's Internal Medicine*, pp. 227-258.

A: Types of arrhythmia according to heart rate:

1. **Tachycardia:** > 100 beats/minute
2. **Bradycardia:** slow heartbeat < 60 beats/minute

B: Types of arrhythmia according to mechanism:

1. **Automaticity:** The sinoatrial node is a single specialized location in the atrium that has a higher automaticity (a faster pacemaker) than the rest of the heart, and therefore, is normally responsible for setting the heart rate and initiating each heartbeat. Any part of the heart that initiates an impulse without waiting for the sinoatrial node is called an ectopic focus and is, by definition, a pathological phenomenon. This may cause a single premature beat now and then, or, if the ectopic focus fires more often than the sinoatrial node, it can produce a sustained abnormal rhythm.
2. **Re-entry arrhythmias:** These occur when an electrical impulse recurrently travels in a tight circle within the heart. There is a heterogeneity of refractory periods and conduction is abnormal in some areas of the myocardial cells. This can produce a sustained abnormal circuit rhythm. These arrhythmias are considered to be the main mechanism of life-threatening cardiac arrhythmias (atrial flutter, paroxysmal supraventricular tachycardia, ventricular tachycardia)
3. **Triggered beats:** Triggered activity refers to a depolarization that occurs after the initial depolarization wave front and comes in two forms, either early or late. Secondary depolarizations that occur before the action potential has fully repolarized are early afterdepolarizations (EADs) and are triggered during prolonged action potentials. Those that occur after the action potential has fully repolarized are delayed afterdepolarizations (DADs) and they result from intracellular calcium overload

C: Types of arrhythmias according to duration:

1. **Isolated premature beats**
2. **Couplets:** 2 beats
3. **Runs:** 3 or more beats
4. **Non-sustained:** Last less than 30 seconds
5. **Sustained:** Last more than 30 seconds

D: Types of arrhythmias according to site of origin:

Supraventricular arrhythmias:

➤ **Atrial arrhythmias**

1. **Sinus bradycardia**

2. **Atrial extrasystoles** (atrial premature beats). This is the early activation of the atria arising from a site other than the sinus node and may be asymptomatic or cause symptoms such as a sensation of "skipping" or palpitations. APBs are often single and isolated but may be frequent and may occur in a bigeminal (every other beat) or other repeated pattern.

3. **Sinus tachycardia**

4. **Atrial tachycardias:**

- **Supraventricular tachycardia** is caused by small areas within the atrial wall other than the SA node that start electrical impulses (ectopic pacemakers). The result is that the atria contract rapidly but with regular rhythm. Can be unifocal or multifocal.
- **Atrial Flutter** is caused by a re-entry rhythm within the atrial wall that starts or passes along impulses that cause the atria to contract rapidly but with a regular rhythm.
- **Atrial fibrillation** is the most common type of arrhythmia, whereby random impulses cause the atria to twitch rapidly and randomly.

➤ **AV junction arrhythmias:**

1. **AV junctional extrasystoles** (atrioventricular junctional premature complexes) are premature cardiac electrical impulses originating from the AV node.
2. **AV junctional rhythms** means that the sinoatrial node does not control the heart's rhythm. Instead, the AV node takes over as the pacemaker.
3. **Atrioventricular nodal re-entrant tachycardia (AVNRT)** is the most common regular, narrow QRS tachycardia. It is more common in women than

men (approximately 75 percent of cases occur in females). It occurs when a re-entrant circuit forms within the AV node. The circuit usually involves two anatomical pathways with different velocity of conduction (fast and slow pathways).

4. **Atrioventricular re-entrant tachycardia** also results from a re-entry circuit, although one physically much larger than AVNRT. One portion of the circuit is usually the AV node, and the other, an abnormal accessory pathway (muscular connection) from the atria to the ventricle. Wolff- Parkinson- White syndrome (WPW) is a relatively common abnormality with an accessory pathway, the bundle of Kent crossing the AV valvular ring.

Ventricular arrhythmias:

1. **Ventricular extrasystoles** (ventricular premature beats)
2. **Ventricular tachycardia** - a type of regular, fast heart rate that arises from improper electrical activity in the ventricles of the heart. It may be divided into monomorphic and polymorphic subtypes, depending on unifocal or multifocal origin. Some VT is associated with reasonable cardiac output and pulse and considered benign compared to pulseless VT, which requires immediate cardio-pulmonary resuscitation and defibrillation.
3. **Ventricular fibrillation** has been described as chaotic asynchronous fractionated activity of the heart. Many random impulses are fired rapidly within the ventricular walls. In ventricular fibrillation the ventricles are quivering instead of beating. When this occurs, it is considered a medical emergency, because the heart cannot effectively pump blood to the body. This is followed by death in the absence of treatment. Treatment is cardio-pulmonary resuscitation and defibrillation.

Atrial Fibrillation and its Treatment With Amiodarone

Atrial fibrillation (AF, Afib) is a form of supraventricular tachyarrhythmia, which is characterized by uncoordinated atrial activation that leads to a decline in the mechanical function of the atria in the heart.

AF is the most common rhythm disturbance in adults. It can be paroxysmal, persistent or permanent. The first registration of AF was recorded by Willem Einthoven in 1906 with his development of electrocardiography. AF affects about 4.5-6 million people in Europe, about 6 million in China and more than 2 million in the USA. More than 60 percent of these patients have symptoms (Laennec & Mcmichael, 1982).

Hemodynamic impairment, thromboembolism and stroke are the most severe complications of AF. Among patients with AF the mortality risk increases twofold and the risk of suffering stroke increases 5-fold compared with normal sinus rhythm patients. As we get older, the risk of developing AF increases. Those over 60 are at 4-6 percent risk, and in 80 year olds and above 9-16 percent (Laennec & Mcmichael, 1982).

The two mechanism of AF are enhanced automaticity from one to two foci and re-entry involving one or more aberrant circuits. The persistence of these mechanisms leads to remodelling of the atria that is characterized by fibrosis and abnormal collagen depositions with fatty infiltration of the SA node, as well as changes in the ion channels and finally apoptosis. In the etiology, multiple causes are important: Tissue ischaemia, due to coronary artery disease; hemodynamic stress caused by increase atrial pressure because of various diseases (e.g. cardiac valve abnormalities, pulmonary hypertension); alcohol and drug use; endocrine diseases; genetic factors; aging; inflammation, etc.

Lately, the role of inflammation and oxidative stress on electrical remodelling and AF has been under research. C-reactive protein (CRP), a major inflammatory marker, has been found to be increased in both persistent and paroxysmal AF. Additionally, CRP may have prognostic significance regarding successful cardioversion of AF (Korantzopoulos et al., 2003; Schnabel et al., 2010)

Figure 2: The potential role of inflammation and oxidative stress in atrial fibrillation-induced electrical re-modeling. I_{CaL} – L-type Ca^{2+} current; APD – action potential duration; AERP – atrial effective refractory period; CV – conduction velocity (Korantzopoulos et al., 2003).

The first observation relating inflammation to AF after cardiopulmonary bypass surgery was made in 1997 by Bruins et al. These investigators reported that the peak incidence of AF on the 2nd–3rd postoperative day coincides with the peak elevation of C-reactive protein (CRP). In 2011, as part of the Framingham cohort study, it was also described that the inflammatory biomarker CRP and neurohormone BNP revealed significant associations with AF among the general population and not just among postoperative patients. BNP was the strongest single biomarker in relation to AF occurrence and significantly improved risk prediction.

Because of the different aetiology, the therapy of AF is multimodal. It involves pharmacological anticoagulation, rate control and rhythm control, as well as electric and surgical therapy. The role of amiodarone is in rhythm control - converting the AF back and then maintaining sinus rhythm. Some antiarrhythmic drugs (e.g. Class Ic) are best to be avoided in AF with structural heart disease because of their slow binding and dissociation from binding sites. However, amiodarone can be used instead because of its multi efficacy. This explains why amiodarone gained popularity in the therapy of AF, as shown in Figure 3 below.

Figure 3: Antiarrhythmic drug selection for the maintenance of sinus rhythm in patients with atrial fibrillation (Piccini & Fauchier, 2016).

There are some properties of amiodarone, though, which cannot make this drug the ultimate solution for AF. For example, it needs a high plasma concentration to be effective, and to reach this time is needed. Therefore, in cases with life-threatening hemodynamic instability where the conversion of AF has to happen as soon as possible, electric cardioversion is the adequate therapy. Additionally, some side effects of amiodarone (e.g. peripheral vasodilatation caused by inhibition of L-type Ca^{2+} channels) would further worsen the patient's state.

In AF there is a faulty electrical pathway in the atria. These pathways can be affected by drugs, but there is another therapeutic option: catheter ablation. This is a procedure to remove or terminate a faulty electrical pathway from sections of the heart of those who are prone to developing cardiac arrhythmias. It can be classified by energy source into radiofrequency ablation and cryoablation. The success rate of a single procedure ranges between 29 percent to 61 percent but with further procedures, better success rates can be obtained. Long term amiodarone therapy has many side effects and is poorly tolerated by many patients. This is one reason why catheter ablation is preferred over amiodarone in maintaining sinus rhythm. The other is success rate. Studies show, that at the end of the first year after catheter ablation, 70 percent of the patients are without recurrence of AF. With treatment of amiodarone the success

rate is only 34 percent. Also, the mortality rate results are significantly better with catheter ablation (8 percent versus 18 percent) (Di Biase et al., 2016).

Amiodarone in cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR)

The American Heart Association and the European Resuscitation Council guidelines recommend the administration of amiodarone for sustained ventricular fibrillation (VF) and ventricular tachycardia (VT) refractory to CPR and defibrillation in sudden cardiac arrests. However, it is a weak recommendation. I was based on clinical trials that compared placebo and amiodarone and showed that amiodarone improved the rate of return of spontaneous circulation (ROSC) but not the survival to hospital discharge and neurological outcome. In 2017 the European Resuscitation Council guideline was updated, and although there is no clear evidence that amiodarone is useful in improving the outcome of CPR, it is still part of the algorithm. In future updates of the guidelines, a further revision of amiodarone's role can be expected, which may remove or replace amiodarone in cardiac arrest guidelines (Pozner et al., 2019).

The up-to-date algorithm of advanced cardiac life support (ACLS) is shown on page 14.

Figure 4: Adult cardiac arrest algorithm (Pozner et al., 2019).

Adult cardiac arrest algorithm

The algorithm presented above has been modified to make it more consistent with the 2015 update to the Advanced Cardiac Life Support (ACLS) Guidelines while we await permission from the American Heart Association to reproduce the latest version.

CPR: cardiopulmonary resuscitation; VF: ventricular fibrillation; VT: ventricular tachycardia; PEA: pulseless electrical activity; IV: intravenous; IO: intraosseous; PETCO₂: post-apneic end tidal carbon dioxide; ET: endotracheal tube.

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Classification of Antiarrhythmic Drugs

Antiarrhythmic agents/drugs are generally classified according to the Vaughan Williams into five main classes. The Vaughan Williams classification was introduced in 1979 by Miles Vaughan Williams. Vaughan Williams was the tutor of Bramah N. Singh, who later contributed to the development of the classification system so now it is sometimes called the Singh–Vaughan Williams classification. Dr. Bramah Singh later became one of the discoverers of amiodarone's antiarrhythmic effect.

The classification of antiarrhythmic drugs is based on the effects of individual drugs on the conduction velocity (a Na^+ channel-dependent effect) and action potential duration (a K^+ channel dependent effect) (Dudley & Cunney, 2004).

The classification of antiarrhythmic drugs by V. Williams was originally based on the effects each drug had on the action potential. Subsequent modifications and enhancements to the system included the molecular targets such as specific ion channels and beta-adrenergic receptors. The latest advances in the classification add extra classes and subclasses to the original four-system classification from the Singh-Vaughan Williams classification. For example, the new Class 0 is a pacemaker channel blocker – ivradabine, and others are experimental or for theoretical targets like Class VI is a gap junction blocker.

This new and modified version of the V. Williams classification has proven to be useful, even though it is a somewhat simplified version of the electrophysiological events that occur. As pointed out above, the classification has five classes from 0-V. These will be briefly described here below, while a summary and the names of individual drugs are shown in Table 1.

- **Class 0** – A new class that modulates the pacemaker channel HCN4, which affects the pacemaker current I_f . The drug ivabradine slows the heart rate (Lei, Wu, Terrar, & Huang, 2018).
- **Class I** – Acts by modulating or blocking the Na^+ channels by inhibiting the phase 0 of depolarization. Class I is subclassified into three subclasses: class Ia, class Ib and class Ic. These subgroups have been put in because their mechanism and duration of action are different, due to the fact that their drug binding to and dissociation from channel receptors are variable (Makielski, MD & Eckhardt, MD, 2019).
 - Class Ia drugs are intermediate regarding speed of binding and dissociation from binding sites.

- Class Ib have the most rapid binding and dissociation from binding sites.
- Class Ic have the slowest binding and dissociation from binding sites.
- **Class II** – Drugs in this class act by inhibiting sympathetic activity, primarily by causing beta blockade, commonly known as beta blockers. They can also have a mild inhibitory effect on the sodium channels (Podrid, Fuchs, & Candinas, 1990). It blocks catecholamine and beta blockers also slow the rate of discharge of the sinus and ectopic pacemakers, which in turn increases the effective refractory period of the AV node (Frishman & Silverman, 1979). Commonly, most beta blockers end with the suffix -olol.
- **Class III** – Drugs in Class III block the potassium channels to inhibit I_{Kr} , I_{Ks} , I_{K1} , and I_{Kur} , thereby prolonging repolarization, the APD, and the refractory period. The relative potency of these drugs for specific potassium currents may account for atrial selectivity; for example, I_{Kur} is only known to be in the atria. Blockage of ventricular potassium currents is manifested on the surface ECG by prolongation of the QT interval, providing the substrate for torsades de pointes, a polymorphic ventricular tachycardia. Amiodarone and dronedarone are exceptions with very little proarrhythmic activity, perhaps because of a balance of offsetting actions. Additionally, there are more atrial-specific agents such as vernakalant that block primarily I_{Kur} (Makielski & Lee, 2019).
- **Class IV** – Drugs in this class are Ca^{2+} channel blockers. Verapamil and diltiazem (the most commonly used drugs in this class) can slow the sinus rate, increase the refractoriness and prolong the conduction through the AV node. They can also prolong the PR interval and depress the left ventricular function.
- **Classes V and VI** – These are newer classes of the V. Williams classification. Drugs in class V are mechanosensitive channel blockers and class VI are gap junction blockers. Drugs in these classes are still open and under investigation. Thus, these classes are still under construction and allow for further extension of the V. Williams classification.

Figure 5 below demonstrates the action and effect of each phase of the cardiac myocyte action potential.

Drugs Affecting the Cardiac Action Potential

Figure 5: This figure gives the reader an idea where and at what phase the classes of antiarrhythmic agent affect the cardiac action potential and its effect on the ECG (Wikipedia, antiarrhythmic agent, 2019).

Additionally, Table 2 demonstrates the cardiac effect of common anti-arrhythmic drugs. It shows their names and when they became approved, their channel effects and what ECG changes should be expected.

Table 1: Names of antiarrhythmic drugs and their places in the Vaughan Williams classification (Makielski & Lee, 2019).

Class 0 (HCN channel blockers)
Ivabradine
Class I (voltage-gated Na⁺ channel blockers)
Class Ia (intermediate dissociation):
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quinidine, ajmaline, disopyramide
Class Ib (rapid dissociation):
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lidocaine, mexilitine
Class Ic (slow dissociation):
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Propafenone, flecainide
Class Id (late current):
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ranolazine
Class II (autonomic inhibitors and activators)
Class IIa (beta blockers):
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nonselective: carvedilol, propranolol, nadolol Selective: atenolol, bisoprolol, betaxolol, celiprolol, esmolol, metoprolol
Class IIb (nonselective beta agonists):
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Isoproterenol
Class IIc (muscarinic M2 receptor inhibitors):
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Atropine, anisodamine, hyoscine, scopolamine
Class IId (muscarinic M2 receptor activators):
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Carbachol, pilocarpine, methacholine, digoxin
Class IIe (adenosine A1 receptor activators):
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adenosine
Class III (K⁺ channel blockers and openers)
Class IIIa (voltage dependent K ⁺ channel blockers):
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ambasilide, amiodarone, dronedarone, dofetilide, ibutilide, sotalol, vernakalant
Class IIIb (metabolically dependent K ⁺ channel openers):
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nicorandil, pinacidil
Class IV (Ca⁺⁺ handling modulators)
Class IVa (surface membrane Ca ⁺⁺ channel blockers):
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bepriidil, diltiazem, verapamil
Class IVb (intracellular Ca ⁺⁺ channel blockers):
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Flecainide, propafenone
Class V (mechanosensitive channel blockers):
No approved medications
Class VI (gap junction channel blockers)
No approved medications
Class VII (upstream target modulators)
Angiotensin converting enzyme inhibitors
Angiotensin receptor blockers
Omega-3 fatty acids
Statins

HCN: hyperpolarization-activated cyclic nucleotide-gated; Na: sodium; K: potassium; Ca: calcium.

Table 2: The cardiac effects of various antiarrhythmic agents (Zimetbaum, 2012).

Antiarrhythmic Drug, Year of Development/Approval	Channel(s) Blocked	ECG Manifestations	Effect on Defibrillation Threshold
Quinidine, 1918	I _{Na} , I _{Kr} , I _{to} , I _{ACh} , α	May ↑ sinus rate; ↑ QT (not dose related); ↑ QRS high dose	↑
Disopyramide, 1962	I _{Na} , I _{Kr} , acetylcholine	May ↑ sinus rate; ↑ QT (not dose related); ↑ QRS high dose	↑
Propafenone, 1976	I _{Na} , β	May ↓ sinus rate, ↑ PR, ↑ QRS	Varies
Flecainide, 1975	I _{Na}	May ↓ sinus rate, ↑ PR, ↑ QRS	↑
Sotalol, 1992, 2000 (AF)	I _{Kr} , β	↓ Sinus rate, may ↑ PR, ↑ QT (dose related)	↓
Dofetilide, 2000 (US only)	I _{Kr}	↑ QT (dose related)	↓
Ibutilide (intravenous), 1995	I _{Kr} , I _{Na} agonist	↑ QT (dose related)	Not relevant
Amiodarone, 1967	I _{Kr} , I _{Na} , I _{Ca} , β, α, acetylcholine	↓ Sinus rate, ↑ PR, ↑ QRS, ↑ QT	↑
Dronedarone, 2009	I _{Kr} , I _{Na} , I _{Ca} , β, α, acetylcholine	↓ Sinus rate, ↑ PR	↑
Vernakalant (intravenous), 2010 (Europe only)	I _{Kur} , I _{Na}	QT prolongation	Not relevant

AF indicates atrial fibrillation; US, United States.

Therapeutic drug monitoring of all classes of antiarrhythmic drugs

Class I antiarrhythmic agents include most of the drugs traditionally thought of as antiarrhythmics and have as a common action the blockade of the fast-inward sodium channel on myocardium. These agents have a very significant toxicity, and while they are being used less, therapeutic drug monitoring (TDM) does significantly increase the safety with which they can be administered. Class II agents are antisympathetic drugs, particularly the β-adrenoceptor blockers. These are generally safe agents which do not normally require TDM. Class III antiarrhythmic agents include sotalol, amiodarone and dronedarone. TDM can be useful in the case of amiodarone to monitor compliance and toxicity. As will be discussed later, many of amiodarone's side effects are dose dependent.

Amiodarone and its metabolites are found in higher concentration in tissues compared with plasma. There is some evidence that plasma concentration above 0,5 µg ml seems to be required for efficacy. However, in the literature there is no convincing data showing a correlation between actual plasma concentrations and antiarrhythmic effect (Rotmensch et al., 1984). While serious toxicity seems to be more likely at concentration above 2,5 µg ml, its incidence is more reliably correlated with measures of total drug usage, suggesting the importance of accumulation in target tissue over time (Jürgens et al., 2003).

Class IV antiarrhythmic drugs are the calcium channel blockers verapamil and diltiazem. These are normally monitored by haemodynamic effects, rather than using TDM. Other agents which do not fall neatly into the Vaughan Williams classification include digoxin and perhexiline.

TDM is very useful for monitoring the administration (and particularly the safety) of both these agents.

Therapeutic drug monitoring has played an extremely important role in the development and clinical application of many agents used to treat cardiac rhythm disturbances. This is particularly true of the Class I agents and of perhexiline and digoxin. TDM has been less important in monitoring the use of β -adrenoceptor blockers and Class IV drugs and has played only a limited role in the use of amiodarone, where there is some value in monitoring for compliance and toxicity. TDM of digoxin and perhexiline will remain important to the practicing cardiologist. There are several new, pure Class III antiarrhythmic agents under development, some of which will definitely require TDM if they come into wide-spread clinical use (Jürgens et al., 2003).

The History of Amiodarone

On its release for human use in 1962, amiodarone was initially marketed as a kind of super or wonder drug. It was kind of stated that it “always works and has no side effects.” However, subsequent clinical trials revealed this not to be the case. In fact, amiodarone side effects are almost certain and can even be very severe and life-threatening.

In 1946, the Russian physiologist Gleb Von Anrep was observing the medical properties of khellin. Khellin is obtained from a plant extract of Khella or Ammi visnaga, which is a very common plant in North-Africa. Anrep became very curious about this plant and its properties when he noticed that one of his technicians had been cured from anginal symptoms after taking khellin. From this it led to the isolation of the active compound from the Khella plant by European pharmaceutical industries (Anrep et al., 1946). By 1961 the Belgian company Labaz had started to manufacture amiodarone and worked on preparations derived from khellin. It soon became very popular in Europe as a treatment for angina pectoris. A doctoral candidate at that time at Oxford University, Bramah

Figure 6: Ammi Visnaga, or Khella plant, from where Khellin is extracted.

Singh, was researching antiarrhythmic properties and whether amiodarone, later also the drug sotalol, had any antiarrhythmic properties. He determined a new class of antiarrhythmic agents (what later came to be known as class III antiarrhythmic agents, as stated previously) (B N Singh & Vaughan Williams, 1970). Barah Singh showed initially with his studies that amiodarone could prolong the AP and the refractory period by its interaction among other functions with K⁺ channels.

It was when the Argentinian physician Mauricio Rosenbaum started to use amiodarone to treat his patients with supraventricular and ventricular arrhythmias that the popularity of amiodarone started to expand. Rosenbaum had demonstrated impressive results on his patients (Rosenbaum et al., 1976). Because of Rosenbaum's paper and results, developed from Singh's theories, physicians in the US began to prescribe amiodarone to their patients with life-threatening arrhythmias that did not respond to any other drugs on the market.

The FDA permitted amiodarone to be used on a compassionate-use basis. Physician in the US obtained the drug from Canada and Europe through the compassionate-use basis by the FDA, but the drug remained unapproved. It has been estimated that during this time more than 10,000 US patients were being treated with amiodarone (Fogoros, 2018). Many physicians started to do trials on their own and began reporting various weird side effects - ocular, skin, pulmonary, hepatic and thyroid. Amiodarone was the most potent at suppressing arrhythmias than any other drug.

As serious side effects such as the difficult thyroid disorders and life-threatening pulmonary toxicity began to be reported, the FDA became reluctant to approve the drug. However, the FDA had no other choice but to approve the drug when European manufacturers of amiodarone threatened to cut off US supply, because they had been supplying the drug for free to thousands and thousands of Americans for more than five years. So, in December 1985 amiodarone became FDA-approved without vast, FDA-sanctioned, randomized clinical trials.

This history of amiodarone makes it one of the very few drugs approved by the FDA without randomized clinical trials. The FDA knew about the recently discovered toxicity, and approved amiodarone only for life-threatening arrhythmias for which no other treatment was feasible. The FDA noted it needed a black-box warning regarding its side effects and urged manufactures to conduct randomized clinical trials to gain formal approval for indications such as atrial fibrillation, noting that these trials would teach us a lot about true incidences and seriousness of the drug's side effects. Those trial where never done, and during that time the patent on the

drug was running out, opening the market for generic manufacturers. Thus amiodarone became restricted by the FDA again, and the use of amiodarone for atrial fibrillation (the most common reason it is prescribed) remains off-label in the US (Fogoros, 2018).

Amiodarone has been available in Europe since 1961. It was initially used and developed for the treatment of angina pectoris. It was not until after 1975 that it was recognized that amiodarone had unique antiarrhythmic properties. It is specifically unique in converting acute- or chronic A. fib to sinus rhythm.

Amiodarone is a class III antiarrhythmic drug (potassium channel blockers). It has a wide range of action and shares its action within all the classes of antiarrhythmic drugs. Its mechanism of action is that amiodarone blocks potassium channels in cardiac muscle cells and also enhances the inward current of sodium channels. Therefore, amiodarone prolongs the action potential. To phrase it differently: it prolongs the Q – T interval on the electrocardiogram (ECG) tracing.

Amiodarone is on the WHO list of essential medicines (*WHO Model List of Essential Medicines*, 2017). It has been approved in Europe and by the FDA for use in VT and V.fib. It has not been approved by the FDA for use in A.fib, but it is in Europe. It is a good cardio converter of tachycardias to sinus rhythm and for use in patients with ICD to minimize shocks. Amiodarone is highly effective in both supraventricular and ventricular arrhythmias.

For further information, amiodarone is manufactured by Pfizer pharmaceuticals. Amiodarone can either be oral tablets or injectable medications. The brand names are *Cordarone*, *Nextrone* and *Pacerone*.

Pharmacology of Amiodarone

To be able to understand amiodarone's therapeutic possibilities, side effects and function, it is vital for us as physicians and medical doctors who might end up prescribing amiodarone to our future patients to understand its structure, mechanism of action, pharmacokinetics and drug interactions.

Chemistry and structure

As mentioned above, amiodarone is derived from the plant extract Khellin. If we look at amiodarone's biochemistry structure, amiodarone is an iodinated benzofuran (highly liposoluble) derivative. Its chemical formula is (2-(4-((2-butyl-1-benzofuran-3-yl) carbonyl-2,6-di-iodophenoxy)ethyl) diethylamine ($C_{25}H_{29}I_2NO_3$). The chemical formula of amiodarone is shown in Figure 7 and the structure of amiodarone is shown in Figure 8. Amiodarone can be divided into three portions – A, B and C.

A: is butyl-benzofuran linked to a carbonyl group.

B: is the carbonyl group linked to di-iodobenzene moiety.

C: then finally it is linked with ether bridge to a tertiary ethylamine.

Figure 7: Chemical formula for Amiodarone - $C_{25}H_{29}I_2NO_3$. (Zipes, Prystowsky, & Heger, 1984)

Figure 8: Structure of Amiodarone (Siddiqui, Khan, & Zaka, 2016)

Pharmacokinetics of amiodarone

The oral bioavailability of amiodarone varies between 22 and 86 percent (averages about 50 percent) (Goldschlager et al., 2007). Its large volume of distribution (66 L/kg) delays the onset of action (2 days to 3 weeks for oral therapy) and results in a long elimination half-life. A 50 percent reduction in serum concentration is seen 3–10 days after cessation of long-term therapy and is followed by a longer terminal half-life of 13–142 days as tissue stores slowly deplete. While amiodarone accumulates in adipose tissue, liver, lung, muscle and the thyroid gland, it is mostly metabolized by the hepatic cytochrome P4503A (CYP3A). Amiodarone's active metabolite N- desethylamiodarone (DEA) has an even longer half-life. Most patients will have approximately equivalent concentrations of amiodarone and DEA at steady state, although DEA levels may exceed those of the parent drug. The "therapeutic" serum range for amiodarone and DEA is 0.5–2.5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. However, serum levels do not correlate well with efficacy or

adverse effects. Regarding therapeutic drug monitoring of amiodarone, it is of little or no importance. It is much better to monitor symptoms and signs of side effects (Trohman et al., 2018).

The inhibitory and inactivation effects on cytochrome P450 provide insight into amiodarone's interaction with other drugs. Amiodarone inactivates CYP3A4, while desethylamiodarone inactivates CYP1A1, CYP1A2, CYP2B6, and CYP2D6. Amiodarone weakly inhibits CYP2C9, CYP2D6, and CYP3A4-mediated activities. Desethylamiodarone competitively inhibits the catalytic activities of CYP2D6 and noncompetitively inhibits CYP2A6, CYP2B6, and CYP3A4. The catalytic activities of CYP1A1, CYP1 A 2, CYP2 C 9, and CYP2 C 19 are also inhibited by desethylamiodarone. The inhibitory effects of desethylamiodarone on each CYP activity are stronger than amiodarone. Amiodarone and DEA are also potent inhibitors of P-glycoprotein-mediated transport (Katoh, Nakajima, Yamazaki, & Yokoi, 2001; Ohyama et al., 2001; Trohman et al., 2018)

Hemodynamic effects of amiodarone

Due to alpha receptor and calcium channel blockade, amiodarone causes coronary and systemic vasodilation with reduced afterload. In intravenous bolus it has a significant negative inotropic effect, capable of decompensating the patient with heart failure, however this effect is not observed with IV slow maintenance dose or chronic oral use, as this effect is adjudicated to the IV excipients (Zaidel, 2019).

Amiodarone interactions with other drugs

Amiodarone is an inhibitor of CYP3A4 and CYP2C9 and is also highly bound to plasma proteins (>96 percent). It can alter the plasma concentration of other highly bound drugs. Additionally, amiodarone can interfere with the hepatic metabolism of several antiarrhythmic drugs (such as quinidine, procainamide, and digoxin), possibly leading to supratherapeutic plasma concentrations if the dose is not reduced. These interactions are particularly worrisome because they can persist for as long as three months after the cessation of therapy due to the long elimination half-life of amiodarone (25 to 100 days) (Zaidel, 2019).

- Amiodarone interference with the metabolism of digoxin raises the levels of plasma digoxin and can lead to digoxin toxicity. The dose of digoxin should be reduced by 50 percent at the time of amiodarone initiation or the need for digoxin should be reevaluated.

Levels of digoxin should be measured 3 days after beginning with amiodarone therapy (Nademanee et al., 1984).

- Amiodarone also interferes with warfarin – a common anticoagulant given to patients with persistent AF to prevent thromboembolic events. A reduction of about 25 percent in warfarin doses is needed to prevent an elevation in the INR and increased risk of bleeding complications (Sanoski et al., 2002). A Swedish cohort study showed that where amiodarone was introduced to patients on chronic warfarin therapy, the average INR increased from 2.6 to 3.1, with average reductions in warfarin dose of about 24.6 percent (Holm et al., 2017). INR levels should be monitored in the first two weeks of initiation of amiodarone therapy.

β-blockers and calcium channel blockers should be administered with caution due to their nodal inhibitory effect. The association with lidocaine for the treatment of episodes of recurrent ventricular tachycardia in the context of myocardial infarction must be carried out with caution since the combined effect of both drugs can cause AV blocks.

Due to its microsomal inhibitory effect, it is usual in therapeutics that when patients with AF are being anticoagulated with warfarin, at the time of initiating amiodarone, the anticoagulant scheme should be reduced to approximately half the dose. With respect to the therapy of AF, in recent years NOACs (apixaban, dabigatran, edoxaban, and rivaroxaban) have been developed, and an interaction mainly between dabigatran and amiodarone has been found at the level of the P- glycoprotein, with a slight increase observed in the doses of dabigatran.

Figure 9: List of amiodarone's drug interactiona and the causative effect (Goldschlager et al., 2007)

Drug	Interaction
Digoxin	Increased concentration and effect with sinus and AV node depression and gastrointestinal tract and neurologic toxicity
Warfarin sodium	Increased concentration and effect
Quinidine, procainamide hydrochloride, or disopyramide	Increased concentration and effect and torsade de pointes ventricular tachycardia
Diltiazem or verapamil	Bradycardia and AV block
β Blockers	Bradycardia and AV block
Flecainide acetate	Increased concentration and effect
Phenytoin	Increased concentration and effect
Anesthetic drugs	Hypotension and bradycardia
Cyclosporine	Increased concentration and effect

Dosage Regimen and Differences Between Oral and Intravenous Use of Amiodarone

This chapter discusses oral and IV dosages and quantities of initial doses. Furthermore, there are sections on bioavailability and how to switch from oral therapy to IV.

Dosage regimen varied very widely, however most clinicians use a loading dose of 600 mg to 2000 mg a day for 1-8 weeks, followed by a reduction to a maintenance dose of the order of 200-400 mg/day. If a rapid loading dose is required, amiodarone may be given intravenously (via a central vein) but the Class III action does not generally appear in the first few hours or even days of administration (Jürgens et al., 2003).

Oral amiodarone

Oral amiodarone is a Class III antiarrhythmic agent as has been previously stated. It prolongs the duration of the action potential and the refractory period of both atrial and ventricular tissue. This effect is primarily a blockage of the rapid component of the delayed rectifier current (IKr) that is responsible for phase 3 repolarization of the action potential.

Like other agents of class III antiarrhythmics it prolongs the QT interval. However, by contrast to most other class III agents, amiodarone causes very little proarrhythmic activity (Giardina et al., 2018).

Oral amiodarone also expresses several other effects that can have therapeutic effects.

- i) It can inhibit the inactivated Na⁺ channels (phase 0), an effect that is seen at rapid heart rates.
- ii) It also shows class II antiarrhythmic drug activity. Amiodarone does so by causing a non-competitive β-receptor blockade.
- iii) Amiodarone also shows some class IV antiarrhythmic drug activity by blocking L-type Ca²⁺ channels.

Administration of oral amiodarone is divided into three parts of dosages or phases: a loading dose, adjustment dose and maintenance dose.

- **Loading dose:** 800 to 1600 mg orally per day for 1 to 3 weeks (occasionally longer) until adequate arrhythmia control is achieved or if side effects become prominent, then switch to adjustment dose.

- **Adjustment dose:** 600 to 800 mg orally per day for 1 month, then switch to maintenance dose.
- **Maintenance dose:** 400 mg orally per day.

Oral amiodarone may be administered once a day; twice a day dosing is recommended for total daily doses of 1000 mg or more or in patients who experience gastrointestinal tolerance. Close monitoring is recommended during the loading phase and surrounding any dose adjustments.

Maintenance dose should be determined according to antiarrhythmic effect as assessed by patient tolerance as well as symptoms, Holter recordings, and/or programmed electrical stimulation; some patients may require up to 600 mg/day while some can be controlled on lower doses (P. Thornton, 2019).

Main usage of oral amiodarone (Cordarone) is to treat life-threatening recurrent VF or life-threatening hemodynamically unstable VT in patients that express inadequate or intolerance to other agents.

Intravenous amiodarone

IV amiodarone has several electrophysiological differences from oral amiodarone administration (Desai et al., 1997; Gomes et al., 1984).

- IV amiodarone causes a smaller increase in the AP duration in the atrial and ventricular myocardium. It also causes a minimal increase in atrial and ventricular refractory periods. Thus, it causes a little or no increase in the duration of the QRS complex or the QT interval.
- IV amiodarone has little effect on the sinus cycle length. It has a vasodilatory activity that triggers an increase in the sympathetic activity, which causes a little or no slowing of the sinus rate.
- IV amiodarone is much more potent and has more rapid antiadrenergic activity.

IV amiodarone, like oral amiodarone, inhibits the inactivated Na⁺ channels, though to a lesser degree than the oral form (Desai et al., 1997).

Initial dose: 1000 mg over the first 24 hours of therapy, delivered by the following infusion regimen:

- Loading infusions: 150 mg over the first 10 minutes (15 mg/min), followed by 360 mg over the next 6 hours (1 mg/min)
- Maintenance infusion: 540 mg over the remaining 18 hours (0.5 mg/min)

Maintenance dose: After the first 24 hours, it is recommended to continue the maintenance infusion rate of 0.5 mg/min. It is possible to increase the infusion rate to achieve effective arrhythmia suppression.

- Supplemental infusions: 150 mg over 10 minutes (15 mg/min) for breakthrough episodes of ventricular fibrillation (VF) or hemodynamically unstable ventricular tachycardia (VT).

Maximum dose: Initial infusion rate of 30 mg/min

Duration of therapy: Until ventricular arrhythmias stabilize (most patients require 48 to 96 hours) maintenance infusion of up to 0.5 mg/min can be continued for up to 3 weeks. Mean daily doses greater than 2100 mg for the first 24 hours are associated with increased risk of hypotension. IV amiodarone is used for the treatment and prophylaxis of frequently recurring VF and hemodynamically unstable VT in patient's refractory to other therapy as well in ACLS.

Transition from IV to oral therapy

The bioavailability of oral compared with intravenous (IV) amiodarone ranges from 30 to 70 percent and is increased in the presence of food. Additionally, an increase in plasma levels may not be seen for four to five hours after the ingestion of oral amiodarone. The following approach to converting IV to oral amiodarone dosing is suggested here below (Goldschlager et al., 2007):

- Patients who have been on IV therapy for more than two weeks can be started on maintenance oral amiodarone at a dose of 200 to 400 mg/day.
- Patients who have been on IV therapy for one to two weeks can be started on an intermediate amiodarone dose of 400 to 800 mg/day. This should be continued until a total loading dose of 10 grams has been received, then the dose should be reduced to the usual maintenance dose of 200 to 400 mg/day.
- Patients who have been on IV therapy for one week or less should probably receive the usual oral amiodarone loading dose of 400 to 1200 mg/day (typically in two divided doses). This should be continued until a total loading dose of 10 grams has

been received, then the dose should be reduced to the usual maintenance dose of 200 to 400 mg/day.

- Both oral and IV therapy can be given concurrently for a few days if there is a concern about gastrointestinal tract function.

For amiodarone there is no need for any specific renal and/or hepatic dose adjustments. To summarize the oral and IV amiodarone therapy, there are some difference in their function and availability. IV is more rapid in action than oral therapy to turn arrhythmic patients towards sinus rhythm. However, to maintain that sinus rhythm, and when the patient is stable, oral therapy should be introduced as quickly as possible. The image here below show a dosage guidelines summary for amiodarone for quick revision.

Figure 10: Dosage guidelines for Amiodarone therapy (Siddoway, 2003).

INDICATION	ADMINISTRATION ROUTE AND SETTING	DOSAGE	POTENTIAL ADVERSE EFFECTS
Life-threatening arrhythmia	IV, inpatient treatment	150-mg IV bolus over 10 minutes (if necessary, bolus may be repeated in 10 to 30 minutes); then 1 mg per minute for 6 hours; then 0.5 mg per minute for 18 hours; then reduce IV dosage or convert to oral dosing when possible. ²	Hypotension, bradycardia, atrioventricular block
Ventricular arrhythmia	Oral, inpatient treatment	800 to 1,600 mg per day in divided doses until a total of 10 g has been given; then 200 to 400 mg per day. ²	Bradycardia, QT prolongation, GI upset, constipation; rarely, torsades de pointes
Atrial fibrillation	Oral, inpatient or outpatient treatment	600 to 800 mg per day in divided doses until a total of 10 g has been given (may use higher initial dosage or IV dosing in unstable inpatients); then 200 mg per day ¹⁰	Bradycardia, QT prolongation, GI upset, constipation; rarely, torsades de pointes

IV = intravenous; GI = gastrointestinal.

Side Effects Caused by Amiodarone

Since amiodarone was first accepted as a treatment for patients with supraventricular and ventricular arrhythmias, clinicians, physicians and pharmacologist have noted and reported side effects and adverse effects related to the drug. Many of the effects are related to dosage of the drug, while others are related to the chemical structure and metabolism of amiodarone. From the vast literature, studies and clinical trials, adverse effects/side effects of amiodarone are in general observed in 75 percent of patients, of which 18 percent and up to 37 percent need to suspend the use of the drug (Zaidel, 2019). It has been shown that unwanted effects seen in patients taking amiodarone can be divided into two broad groups. One group of effects is dosage related, while the other group of effects is both dosage- and duration-dependent (Harris et al., 1983).

Toxic effects of amiodarone can be divided into three groups: cardiac toxic effects, non-cardiac toxic effects and thyroid toxicity.

- i) Cardiac toxic effects: bradycardia, heart block in patients with sinus or AV nodal diseases.
- ii) Non-cardiac toxic effects: amiodarone accumulates in tissues, e.g. heart, lung, liver and skin. Of these, pulmonary accumulation can lead to fatal pulmonary fibrosis. Amiodarone can cause abnormal hepatic tears and hepatitis. In skin it can cause photodermatitis and grey/purple skin discoloration in sun-exposed areas. Ocular effects occur.
- iii) Thyroid toxicity: amiodarone blocks the peripheral conversion of T4 to T3, so it may result in either hypo- or hyperthyroidism.

The following table below is reconstructed from the article by R.G. Trohman et al., 2018, and shows the percentages of the most common and severe side effects caused by amiodarone and long-term amiodarone therapy.

Table 3: Side effects and toxicity caused by amiodarone (Trohman et al., 2018).

Adverse effect	Prevalence and/or annual incidence
Corneal microdeposits	> 90%
Optic neuropathy/neuritis	< 1%–2%
Hypothyroidism	5%–10%
Hyperthyroidism	0.9%–10%
Photosensitivity	25%–75%
Blue-gray skin discoloration	4%–9%
Pulmonary toxicity	1%–17%
Elevated liver enzyme levels	15%–30%
Hepatitis and cirrhosis	< 3%; 0.6%/yr.
Tremor and ataxia	3%–35%
Peripheral neuropathy	0.3%/yr.
Bradycardia and AV block	3%–5%
Torsades de Pointes	< 1%
Hypotension (IV formulation)	15–26%

Insomnia, memory disturbances and delirium have also been reported.

Ocular changes

The main ocular changes are in the form of microdeposits as reported by ophthalmologist and occur in almost 100 percent of patients during first 1-2 months of treatment with amiodarone. This is, however, not a reason for discontinuing the drug. Microdeposits will resolve on their own after 3-4 months. The microdeposits are usually not symptomatic. However, the development of blurred vision, photophobia and blue/green halos occur seldom but are a reason for giving up treatment with the drug (Shukla, Jowett, Thompson, & Pohl, 1994).

Amiodarone dermatopathies

Patients that are treated with amiodarone mainly experience two types of skin reaction. In approximately 75 percent of dermatopathies reported is photosensitivity. Intense sunburn during mild sun exposure over summer months, erythema, swelling. It varies between patients if they experience any skin reaction in the beginning of therapy or after long-term usage. It has been reported that patients who have been taking amiodarone (600mg/day for more than 2 years) can develop grey/purple pigmentation as can be seen in Figure 9. In these patients that develop alterations in their skin colour, they have had high plasma concentration of amiodarone (>3,1 mg/l) and desethyl amiodarone (3,2 mg/l). Biopsies have been taken from

Figure 11: Slate-gray facial pigmentation in a patient who has taken amiodarone for more than 2 years (Harris et al., 1983).

the affected skin areas and shown an increase in the deposits of lipofuscin. It has also been reported that melanin is reduced in the affected skin areas (Harris et al., 1983). It has also been hypothesised in a journal article by Harris et al. that photosensitivity comes prior to elastic degeneration, lipofuscin deposition and skin discoloration.

Hepatotoxicity side effects of amiodarone

A rise in serum aminotransferase concentrations occurs in approximately 25 percent (range 15 to 50 percent) of patients soon after amiodarone therapy has begun (Lewis et al., 1989). The patients are usually asymptomatic, but the drug should be discontinued if there is more than a twofold elevation (Goldschlager et al., 2007). Symptomatic hepatitis occurs in less than 3 percent of patients; potential complications include cirrhosis and hepatic failure. As a result, it is recommended that liver function tests be monitored at baseline and every six months.

Jaundice is an unusual side effect that may be due to intrahepatic cholestasis. Serum bilirubin concentrations may first increase or continue to increase for a period of time after the drug is discontinued. These findings are consistent with the long half-life of amiodarone (25 to 100 days).

The histopathologic features of amiodarone-induced hepatotoxicity include Mallory bodies, steatosis, intralobular inflammatory infiltrates, fibrosis, and phospholipidosis. These changes are like those in alcoholic liver disease. The presence of phospholipid-laden lysosomal lamellar bodies on electron microscopy may help distinguish amiodarone hepatotoxicity from alcoholic liver disease (Giardina et al., 2019).

Gastrointestinal side effects

Gastrointestinal side effects associated with amiodarone therapy include nausea, vomiting, anorexia, diarrhoea, and constipation. They have been described in up to 30 percent of patients (see table of adverse reaction), mostly during the initial loading phase of therapy. In the meta-analysis of trials of chronic low-dose amiodarone therapy, gastrointestinal side effects were not significantly more frequent than with placebo (Giardina et al., 2019).

Neurological side effects

Neurologic toxicity may take many forms, including tremor, ataxia, peripheral neuropathy with paraesthesias, and sleep disturbances. These effects, which have been described in 3 to 30 percent of patients, appear to be dose-related, being more common during initial loading or in patients requiring higher doses. In the meta-analysis of trials of chronic low-dose amiodarone therapy (mean dose 150 to 330 mg/day), neurologic side effects were much less common than reported in early studies that utilized higher doses of amiodarone, but still significantly more frequent than with placebo (4.6 versus 1.9 percent, OR 2.0, 95 percent CI 1.1-3.7). A retrospective study of 707 patients in Olmsted County treated with amiodarone arrived at a similar conclusion (Goldschlager et al., 2007; Orr et al., 2009; Vorperian et al., 1997)

Amiodarone Pulmonary side effects

Amiodarone therapy can lead to several forms of pulmonary toxicity, including interstitial pneumonitis (the most common presentation), eosinophilic pneumonia, organizing pneumonia, acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), diffuse alveolar haemorrhage (DAH), pulmonary nodules and masses, but rarely pleural effusions. The incidence of pulmonary toxicity from amiodarone is not precisely known; it is estimated to be 1 to 5 percent. Pulmonary side effects

caused by amiodarone are dose dependent. The higher the dose, the more likely patients are to develop pulmonary side effects.

Risk factors for amiodarone-induced pulmonary toxicity include a daily dose of ≥ 400 mg/day, duration of therapy exceeding two months, patient age >60 years, pre-existing lung disease, surgery, and pulmonary angiography.

If pulmonary side effects develop, the primary therapy is to cease amiodarone therapy altogether.

Interstitial pneumonitis due to amiodarone toxicity is characterized by the insidious onset of non-productive cough and/or dyspnoea. Fever, pleuritic pain, weight loss, and malaise can also occur. The onset of symptoms is usually 6 to 12 months of amiodarone therapy but may occur within two months or after several years of treatment.

The chest radiograph typically reveals new focal or diffuse reticular or ground glass opacities. High-resolution computed tomography (HRCT) of the chest and upper abdomen usually shows ground glass and reticular opacities and increased attenuation in the lungs, liver, and spleen (Figure 12). Pulmonary function tests typically show restriction and a reduced diffusing capacity (DLCO).

Figure 12: HRCT showing extensive and severe bilateral ground glass opacities due to long-term therapy by amiodarone (Sweidan et al., 2016).

A clinical diagnosis of amiodarone-induced interstitial pneumonitis can often be made when the clinical features are consistent; other possibilities (e.g. infection, heart failure) have been excluded; and the patient improves with drug cessation and, possibly, a trial of glucocorticoid therapy. Lung biopsy is usually deferred unless the diagnosis remains uncertain after a trial of drug cessation.

In addition to cessation of amiodarone, for most patients with more than mild symptoms of interstitial pneumonitis due to amiodarone, systemic glucocorticoid therapy is recommended. The usual dose is the equivalent of oral prednisone 40 to 60 mg/day. Due to the long elimination

half-life (approximately 45 days) of amiodarone, pulmonary toxicity may initially progress despite drug discontinuation and may recur upon glucocorticoid withdrawal (Chan et al., 2019; Colby et al., 2017; Sweidan et al., 2016).

Other types of pneumonia can develop, as mentioned above in this chapter, but detailed discussion will not be included here as these are very rare complications and do not often occur.

Amiodarone and thyroid side effects

Amiodarone effects on the thyroid gland are today well known and studies have shown and proven that it causes either hypo- or hyperthyroidism. These side effects can be divided into intrinsic effects resulting from inherent properties of the compound and iodine-induced effects that are solely due to the pharmacological effects caused by iodine overload. These effects are summarized in Figure 13. As stated above, amiodarone is a very iodine-rich compound (37.3 percent of its molecular weight is iodine). Amiodarone itself even has structural similarity to the thyroid hormone. Even low dose oral therapy (200 mg daily) can elevate daily iodine intake by 50-100 times (Martino et al., 2001). It has been stated in the past that incidences of amiodarone-induced thyroid dysfunction ranged between 2 to 24 percent (Albert, Alves, & Rose, 1987). In more recent reviews of the literature it is said that hypothyroidism occurs in 5-10 percent and hyperthyroidism occurs in approximately 0.9-10 percent of amiodarone patients. Due to this fact, amiodarone side effects have been shown to be in many cases dose-related and that also correlates with thyroid side effects. Recently it has been shown that lower amiodarone dose therapy (152-330mg daily) reduces thyroid side effects significantly and incidences of thyroid dysfunction are 3.7 percent (Trohman et al., 2018)

Figure 13: Mechanism by which amiodarone affects thyroid hormone metabolism (TH=thyroid hormone) (Basaria & Cooper, 2005).

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The structure of amiodarone, however, is such that it contains 75mg of organic iodine (I) per 200mg of active dose. During biotransformation, the drug is de-iodinated and studies have estimated that in a dose of 200mg of amiodarone some 6 mg of free iodine are released (Wiersingal & Trip, 1986).

Amiodarone induced hypothyroidism (AIH)

As noted previously, amiodarone is iodine rich. Large amounts of amiodarone released during the amiodarone metabolism inhibit the thyroid hormone biosynthesis and release the so-called Wolff-Chaikoff effect (Harjai et al., 1997; Vorperian et al. , 1997). The Wolff-Chaikoff effect is known as an autoregulatory phenomenon which inhibits organification in the thyroid gland, the formation of thyroid hormone inside the thyroid follicle, and release of thyroid hormones into the blood stream. Acute Wolff-Chaikoff effect lasts for a few days, and through the so-called escape from Wolff-Chaikoff effect the levels of intrathyroidal iodide and normal synthesis of T4 and T3 returns to normal.

Amiodarone induced hypothyroidism usually resolves in 2-4 months after cessation of the amiodarone therapy. However, persistent AIH despite withdrawal is in direct correlation with underlying autoimmune thyroid diseases such as Hashimoto thyroiditis. AIH is slightly more frequent in females, with female to male ratio of 1.5:1 (Trohman et al., 2018). Hypothyroidism may develop as early as within two weeks or as late as after 39 months after the amiodarone therapy has been initiated.

Although IV administration has twice more bioavailability than oral therapy, according to the latest literature it is unlikely that short administration of IV amiodarone can induce AIH. It is more likely that it is due to long term oral therapy.

AIH patients usually show very vague signs and symptoms. These symptoms are like those seen in patients with spontaneous hypothyroidism: cool, pale, dry skin, fatigue, cold intolerance, slow speech and mental sluggishness are common. Slow movement, dyspnoea on exertion and decreased exercise capacity caused by hypothyroidism may be difficult to distinguish from baseline or normal progressive cardiopulmonary abnormalities. For the management of patients who develop AIH and due to the high degree of efficacy, amiodarone is often the only antiarrhythmic option for the patient and administration is usually continued with levothyroxine (L-T4) replacement. T4 is thus the drug of choice in these conditions, especially in patients with cardiac problems, because it requires once-daily administration and is not associated with spikes in serum thyroid hormones. It needs to be kept in mind that it is advisable to keep the serum Thyroid hormone in the upper half of the normal range of TSH (Trohman et al., 2018).

Amiodarone induced hyperthyroidism (AIT)

There are two types of AIT. In type I, there is increased synthesis of thyroid hormone, whereas in type II there is excess release of T4 and T3 due to a destructive thyroiditis. However, it is often difficult to distinguish between the two types and some patients may have elements of both. The 24-hour radioiodine uptake is typically not able to distinguish between types I and II AIT, because the high levels of ingested iodine with amiodarone result in 24-hour uptakes of less than 1 percent in most patients with either type I or type II AIT. Technetium-99m (99mTc)-sestamibi imaging, where available, or colour flow Doppler sonography (CFDS) may be the best ways of distinguishing between the two types of AIT.

In patients who develop AIT and to whom amiodarone was prescribed for life-threatening ventricular arrhythmias, it is suggested continuing the amiodarone therapy and treating the hyperthyroidism as well. If the amiodarone was not prescribed for life-threatening ventricular arrhythmias, the literature suggests discontinuing the drug. In the case of type I AIT amiodarone should not be stopped until the hyperthyroid symptoms are well under control with thionamides therapy.

Type I AIT is hyperthyroidism with increased synthesis of T4 and T3; the excess iodine provides increased substrate, resulting in enhanced thyroid hormone production. It is suggested to use thionamides as first-line drug to treat type I AIT. Higher than average doses of thionamides are usually needed (30 to 40 mg of methimazole or 450 to 600 mg propylthiouracil (PTU) daily). Perchlorate or lithium are sometimes added to speed recovery; however, perchlorate is not available in the United States. In addition, perchlorate has been associated, albeit rarely, with aplastic anaemia.

Type II AIT is a destructive thyroiditis that results in the release of excess T4 and T3, but not increased synthesis. It is typically seen in patients without underlying thyroid disease and is caused by a direct toxic effect of amiodarone on the thyroid gland. The hyperthyroid phase may last from several weeks to several months and is often followed by a hypothyroid phase and then recovery. For the treatment and management of type II AIT, it is recommended to give glucocorticoids as first line treatment, commonly prednisone 40 to 60 mg/day is given and therapy continued for 1-2 months, before tapering.

If the mechanism of amiodarone-induced hyperthyroidism is uncertain, it is recommended to consider a mixture between type I and type II AIT. The mainstay therapy in these cases is a combination of prednisone 40 mg/day and methimazole 40 mg/day. If there is a rapid response,

type II AIT can be suggested and methimazole can be tapered or stopped. Poor response suggests type I AIT (Basaria et al., 2005; Ross, n.d.; Trohman et al., 2018).

The following algorithm by Trohman et al. 2018 gives a good overview of the thyroid follow-up and treatment.

Figure 14: Algorithm showing the thyroid follow-up and treatment suggested for patients receiving amiodarone (Trohman et al., 2018).

Frequency of long-term side effects using oral amiodarone

A study by Greene et al. focuses on the long-term side effects on 70 patients who were treated with oral amiodarone. They were given a 1200 mg/day loading dose for 7 days and 600 mg/day after that for at least 6-12 months on average with a follow-up after 6 months. Side effects occurred in 93 percent of the patients and 19 percent of the patients needed to discontinue their medication. 56 patients had gastrointestinal side effects, most commonly constipation. All patients except one developed corneal microdeposits. Cardiovascular side effects were

uncommon, while symptomatic pulmonary side effects occurred in 7 patients with pulmonary toxicity in 5 patients. Neurological side effects occurred in 52 patients, most commonly tremor and ataxia. Thyroid dysfunction occurred in 3 patients and 32 patients had skin abnormalities (Greene et al., 1983). As for pulmonary side effects, they have been noted to resolve on withdrawal of amiodarone alone or with a reduction of the dose (Zipes, Prystowsky, & Heger, 1984).

Figure 15: Summary from the two chapters above showing concise information about incidences, diagnosis and treatment of side effects caused by amiodarone.

Reaction	Incidence, %	Diagnosis*	Management
Pulmonary	1-20	Cough, especially with local or diffuse infiltrates on chest x-ray film, suggesting interstitial pneumonitis; and decrease in D_LCO from baseline	Usually discontinue drug; corticosteroids may be considered; occasionally, can continue drug if levels high and abnormalities resolve; rarely, continue amiodarone with corticosteroid if no other option
Gastrointestinal tract	30	Nausea, anorexia, and constipation	Symptoms may decrease with decrease in dose
	15-50	AST or ALT level greater than 2 times normal	If hepatitis considered, exclude other causes
	<3	Hepatitis and cirrhosis	Consider discontinuation, biopsy, or both to determine whether cirrhosis is present
Thyroid	1-22	Hypothyroidism	Thyroxine
	<3	Hyperthyroidism	Corticosteroids, propylthiouracil or methimazole, and may need thyroidectomy
Skin	<10	Blue discoloration	Reassurance and sunblock
	25-75	Photosensitivity	Sunblock
Central nervous system	3-30	Ataxia, paresthesias, peripheral polyneuropathy, sleep disturbance, impaired memory, and tremor	Often dose dependent, and improve or resolve with dose adjustment
Ocular	<5	Halo vision, especially at night	Corneal deposits the norm; if optic neuritis occurs, discontinue
	1	Optic neuritis	
	>90	Photophobia, visual blurring, and microdeposits	
Heart	5	Bradycardia and AV block	May need permanent cardiac pacing
	<1	Proarrhythmia	May need to discontinue the drug
Genitourinary	<1	Epididymitis and erectile dysfunction	Pain may resolve spontaneously

* D_LCO indicates diffusion capacity of carbon monoxide; AST, aspartate aminotransferase; and ALT, alanine aminotransferase.

Monitoring and Follow-up on Patients Being Treated with Amiodarone

As already stated, amiodarone can cause and/or lead to many adverse effects. Patients being treated with amiodarone for a long term require proper management and follow-up. The prevalence of developing adverse effects is as high as 15 percent in the first year, and almost 50 percent of patients being treated with amiodarone for longer than a year develop adverse effects. Many of the side effects are manageable and cessation of amiodarone therapy due to serious side effects is less than 20 percent (Goldschlager et al., 2007). Therefore, it is vital for physicians treating patients with amiodarone to be aware in the follow-up visits of certain aspects of the history of the patient during the physical examination as well as what routine

laboratory evaluations to ask for. The table below demonstrates in more detail the adverse side effects amiodarone can cause and also gives a simplified overview of what laboratory testing should be monitored and the time frame by which they should be performed.

Table 3: Routine laboratory testing in patients receiving amiodarone (Goldschlager et al., 2007).

Type of Test†	Time When Test Is Performed
Liver function tests	Baseline and every 6 mo
Thyroid function tests (T ₄ and TSH)	Baseline and every 6 mo
Serum creatinine and electrolytes	Baseline and as indicated
Chest x-ray film	Baseline and then yearly
Ophthalmologic evaluation	At baseline if visual impairment or for symptoms
Pulmonary function tests (including D _L CO)	Baseline and for unexplained dyspnea, especially in patients with underlying lung disease; and if there are suggestive x-ray film abnormalities
ECG	Baseline and every year

*If clinical circumstances warrant, more frequent follow-up will be necessary.

†T₄ indicates thyroxine; TSH, thyrotropin; D_LCO, diffusion capacity of carbon monoxide; and ECG, electrocardiogram.

Dronedarone, Amiodarone's Little Brother

Within the literature and dozens of previous studies, it has been shown that amiodaron's iodine moieties and extreme lipophilic nature and accumulation in tissues are strongly related to its toxicity. Also, amiodarone's long half-life can cause side effects that may even persist after treatment has been halted. Thus, because of amiodarone's vast and profound anti-arrhythmic possibilities, focus has been placed on the development of amiodarone derivatives that lack the iodine moieties, are less lipophilic, and have shorter half-life than amiodarone. Hence the development of dronedarone (Heijman & Dobrev, 2013).

Dronedarone, the first noniodinated amiodarone congener, has been developed largely to obtain the antiarrhythmic efficacy in the control of atrial fibrillation without the known adverse side effects of amiodarone (Singh & Cingolani, 2010). Dronedarone (known as Multaq) is a benzofuran derivative with antiarrhythmic properties belonging to all four Vaughan-Williams classes, like amiodarone. Dronedarone is specifically indicated to reduce the risk of cardiovascular hospitalization in patients with paroxysmal or persistent atrial fibrillation (AF) or atrial flutter (AFL), with a recent episode of AF/AFL and associated cardiovascular risk

factors who are in sinus rhythm or who will be cardioverted. Dronedarone is supplied as a 400 mg tablet designed for oral administration. The recommended initial dose of the drug is 400 mg twice daily, once in the morning with a meal and once in the evening with a meal.

Dronedarone (Multaq) became approved by the FDA in July 2009, and the ATHENA, EURIDIS and ADONIS trials were the main trials for its approval (Dobrev & Nattel, 2010; Passmann & Giardina, 2019). The DIONYSOS trial from 2010 showed that dronedarone led to lower incidence of adverse thyroid, neurologic, skin and ocular effects in patients with AF compared with amiodarone, however it was less effective. Dronedarone also does not have superiority regarding safety profile compared with other antiarrhythmic drugs for the treatment of AF (Le Heuzey et al., 2010). The DIONYSOS trial tested dronedarone versus amiodarone in patients with persistent AF. During a seven-month follow-up after cardioversion, the recurrence of AF was higher in those patients being treated with dronedarone compared with patients treated with amiodarone (63.5 percent vs. 42 percent), but discontinuation of dronedarone versus amiodarone was less frequent (10.4 percent vs. 13.3 percent). The data from this trial suggests and shows that tolerability for dronedarone is higher but its efficacy is less compared with amiodarone (Dobrev et al., 2010).

The Future of Amiodarone and Other Antiarrhythmics

A recent multicentred randomized study from 2016 demonstrated that catheter ablation of AF is superior to amiodarone therapy in achieving freedom from AF at long term follow-up as well as reducing unplanned hospitalization and mortality in patients with heart failure and persistent AF. Catheter ablation appears to be the treatment of choice for this patient group (Di Biase et al., 2016).

In the Amio-Cat trial from 2014, in which 212 patients underwent AF ablation, a randomized trial was carried out with amiodarone or placebo for eight weeks following the catheter ablation. There was a nonsignificant trend toward fewer recurrences of AF in the amiodarone group (39 percent versus 48 percent), but among those treated with amiodarone there were significantly fewer patients who required hospitalization or cardioversion for recurrent AF (Darkner et al., 2014).

Research has shown that amiodarone has unique pharmacological properties, and that it still has an important role in the treatment of several cardiovascular diseases (Zaidel, 2019).

Vernakalant, a new drug under development

Vernakalant is considered a relatively “atrially-selective” antiarrhythmic agent since one of its main actions is to inhibit the ultrarapid potassium current (IKur) and the acetylcholine potassium current (IKAch), both of which are predominantly found in the atria. Vernakalant also mildly inhibits other potassium channels and, to a much lesser extent, the sodium current. The program for vernakalant drug development in the US has been terminated. The drug is available in an intravenous form to terminate AF in Europe.

Like other class III antiarrhythmics, vernakalant blocks atrial potassium channels, thereby prolonging repolarization. It differs from typical class III agents by blocking a certain type of potassium channel, the cardiac transient outward potassium current, with increased potency as the heart rate increases. This means that it is more effective at high heart rates, while other class III agents tend to lose effectiveness under these circumstances. It also slightly blocks the hERG potassium channel, leading to a prolonged QT interval. This may theoretically increase the risk of ventricular tachycardia, though this does not seem to be clinically relevant (Dobrev & Nattel, 2010). The drug also blocks atrial sodium channels. It is mainly used for rapid conversion of acute-onset AF (AF lasting 3 to 72 hours).

Because of the complexity of underlying mechanisms and large variability in pathophysiology, a variety of therapeutic options will continue to be needed for individual patients. Thus it will be a future challenge to identify precisely what treatment approach and timing will be suitable for individual patients.

Use of Amiodarone in Children

The efficacy, safety and adverse effects of amiodarone have been proven in adults. However, the use of amiodarone in tachyarrhythmias in children and dosage has not yet been very well established. A small clinical trial, a double blinded study from 2005, showed that the overall efficacy of IV amiodarone in children was dose related and had no significant effect on any specific subgroup of arrhythmias and its use in children is often limited by toxicities (Saul et al., 2005)

Adverse effects in children are very common and highly likely with IV amiodarone administration. These include cardiovascular collapse, hypotension, bradycardia and AV block. Nausea and vomiting are also common. When administering IV amiodarone to children,

continuous ECG and blood pressure monitoring should be performed (Giardina & Passman, 2018).

Amiodarone administration in children appears to be effective in several circumstances according to the intravenous amiodarone trial on children from 2005. They are listed here below.

- a) Supraventricular tachycardia (SVT): For children who have refractory SVT, IV amiodarone is an option as second-line therapy for conversions to sinus rhythm and oral amiodarone is a second-line therapy for the prevention of recurrent arrhythmia. Oral amiodarone is sometimes used for chronic management if there is bad or no response to first- and second-line drugs (e.g. beta blockers, digoxin and sotalol).
- b) Wide QRS complex tachycardia: IV amiodarone can be, and has been, used alone or in combination with other antiarrhythmic drugs in infants and children with life-threatening ventricular tachyarrhythmias and shown good results (Perry et al., 1996).

Further studies of the usage of IV or oral amiodarone in less critically ill children are still to be carried out. However, the use of IV and oral amiodarone in critically ill children with tachyarrhythmias has proved to be safe, effective and even life-saving when standard therapy is ineffective (Perry et al., 1996).

Conclusion

The vast amount of research and literature available on amiodarone leaves one in no doubt about its therapeutic potential. No other antiarrhythmic drug available on the market today can come close to amiodarone's many pleiotropic effects. Drugs such as dronedarone and vernakalant have been developed to mimic amiodarone's function. However, their efficacy is less than of amiodarone, but their only positive side is that they have less side effects compared to amiodarone.

Despite lack of clinical trials in the early days of amiodarone, it still shows a significant superiority over other antiarrhythmic drugs. It has, in fact, an effect on all classes and phases of the action potential of cardio myocytes.

With better tools and better knowhow of surgical and ICD devices, cardiac pathologies such as AF can be treated quite well. However, amiodarone's role in modern medicine is still of utmost importance to further treat and manage the whole spectrum of arrhythmias where other drugs show less efficacy of treating such pathologies.

Although chronic use of amiodarone and frequent prescriptions of the drug have significantly decreased, it still has its function and will still be the wonder drug for the management of patients with AF, Vtach and persistent ventricular tachycardia that cannot be managed by any other means than pharmacologically.

If we had to prove with one example why amiodarone is such an important drug in today's medicine, it would be that even though there is no clear evidence of its efficacy, amiodarone still remains the recommended drug in the sudden cardiac arrest treatment protocol.

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I would like to conclude this with a quote from Sir Winston Churchill which I have chosen as my motto: “Success is not final, failure is not fatal: it is the courage to continue that counts.”

Bibliography

- Albert, S. G., Alves, L. E., & Rose, E. P. (1987). Thyroid dysfunction during chronic amiodarone therapy. *Journal of the American College of Cardiology*, 9(1), 175–183. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0735-1097\(87\)80098-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0735-1097(87)80098-0)
- Anrep, G. V, Barsoum, G. S., Kenawy, M. R., & Misrahy, G. (1946). AMMI VISNAGA IN THE TREATMENT OF THE ANGINAL SYNDROME. *British Heart Journal*, 8(4), 171–177. Retrieved from <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/18610042>
- Basaria, S., & Cooper, D. S. (2005). Amiodarone and the thyroid. *The American Journal of Medicine*, 118, 706–714. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amjmed.2004.11.028>
- Chan, E. D., & King, T. E. (n.d.). Amiodarone pulmonary toxicity. Retrieved April 5, 2019, from 2018 website: https://www.uptodate.com/contents/amiodarone-pulmonary-toxicity?source=bookmarks_widget
- Colby, R., & Geyer, H. (2017). Amiodarone-induced pulmonary toxicity. *Journal of the American Academy of Physician Assistants*. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.JAA.0000524713.17719.c8>
- Darkner, S., Chen, X., Hansen, J., Pehrson, S., Johannessen, A., Nielsen, J. B., & Svendsen, J. H. (2014). Recurrence of arrhythmia following short-term oral AMIODarone after CATHeter ablation for atrial fibrillation: A double-blind, randomized, placebo-controlled study (AMIO-CAT trial). *European Heart Journal*, 35(47), 3356–3364. <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurheartj/ehu354>
- Desai, A. D., Chun, S., & Sung, R. J. (1997). The Role of Intravenous Amiodarone in the Management of Cardiac Arrhythmias. *Annals of Internal Medicine*, 127(4), 294. <https://doi.org/10.7326/0003-4819-127-4-199708150-00007>
- Di Biase, L., Mohanty, P., Mohanty, S., Santangeli, P., Trivedi, C., Lakkireddy, D., ... Natale, A. (2016a). Ablation Versus Amiodarone for Treatment of Persistent Atrial Fibrillation in Patients With Congestive Heart Failure and an Implanted Device: Results From the AATAC Multicenter Randomized Trial. *Circulation*, 133(17), 1637–1644. <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.115.019406>
- Di Biase, L., Mohanty, P., Mohanty, S., Santangeli, P., Trivedi, C., Lakkireddy, D., ... Natale, A. (2016b). Ablation Versus Amiodarone for Treatment of Persistent Atrial Fibrillation in Patients With Congestive Heart Failure and an Implanted Device. *Circulation*, 133(17), 1637–1644. <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.115.019406>
- Dobrev, D., & Nattel, S. (2010). New antiarrhythmic drugs for treatment of atrial fibrillation. *The Lancet*, 375(9721), 1212–1223. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(10\)60096-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(10)60096-7)
- Dudley, S. C., & Cunney, M. B. (2004). *STATEMENT OF Antiarrhythmic PUBLISHING STAFF Rational Choices in Antiarrhythmic Pharmacotherapy*. 10, 1–2.
- Fogoros, R. N. (2018). The Strange History of Amiodarone. Retrieved May 18, 2019, from <https://www.verywellhealth.com/the-strange-history-of-amiodarone-1745987>
- Frishman, W., & Silverman, R. (1979). Clinical pharmacology of the new beta-adrenergic blocking drugs. Part 2. Physiologic and metabolic effects. *American Heart Journal*, 97(6), 797–807. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0002-8703\(79\)90016-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0002-8703(79)90016-4)

- Giardina, E.-G., & Passman, R. (2018). Amiodarone: Clinical uses. Retrieved April 5, 2019, from UpToDate website:
https://www.uptodate.com/contents/search?search=amiodarone&sp=0&searchType=PLAIN_TEXT&source=USER_INPUT&searchControl=TOP_PULLDOWN&searchOffset=1&autoComplete=true&language=&max=0&index=0~6&autoCompleteTerm=ami
- Giardina, E.-G., & Zimetbaum, P. J. (2019). *Amiodarone: Monitoring and management of side effects - UpToDate*. Retrieved from
https://www.uptodate.com/contents/amiodarone-monitoring-and-management-of-side-effects?source=history_widget#H22
- Goldschlager, N., Epstein, A. E., Naccarelli, G. V., Olshansky, B., Singh, B., Collard, H. R., & Murphy, E. (2007). A Practical Guide for Clinicians Who Treat Patients with Amiodarone: 2007. *Heart Rhythm*, 4(9), 1250–1259.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hrthm.2007.07.020>
- Gomes, J. A. C., Kang, P. S., Hariman, R. J., El-Sherif, N., & Lyons, J. (1984). Electrophysiologic effects and mechanisms of termination of supraventricular tachycardia by intravenous amiodarone. *American Heart Journal*, 107(2), 214–221.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/0002-8703\(84\)90367-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0002-8703(84)90367-3)
- Greene, H. L., Graham, E. L., Werner, J. A., Sears, G. K., Gross, B. W., Gorham, J. P., ... Trobaugh, G. B. (1983). Toxic and therapeutic effects of amiodarone in the treatment of cardiac arrhythmias. *Journal of the American College of Cardiology*, 2(6), 1114–1128.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0735-1097\(83\)80338-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0735-1097(83)80338-6)
- Harjai, K. J., & Licata, A. A. (1997). Effects of Amiodarone on Thyroid Function. *Annals of Internal Medicine*, 126(1), 63. <https://doi.org/10.7326/0003-4819-126-1-199701010-00009>
- Harris, L., McKenna, W. J., Rowland, E., Holt, D. W., Storey, G. C., & Krikler, D. M. (1983). Side effects of long-term amiodarone therapy. *Circulation*, 67(1), 45–51.
<https://doi.org/10.1161/01.CIR.67.1.45>
- Heijman, J., & Dobrev, D. (2013). Pleiotropic actions of amiodarone: still puzzling after half a century. *Naunyn-Schmiedeberg's Archives of Pharmacology*, 386(7), 571–574.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00210-013-0865-0>
- Herold G. *Herold's Internal Medicine : A Lecture Oriented Systematic and Accurate Representation of the Complete Topic Catalogue for the Medical Examination for Physicians*. Forfatteren; 2014.
- Holm, J., Lindh, J. D., Andersson, M. L., & Mannheimer, B. (2017). The effect of amiodarone on warfarin anticoagulation: a register-based nationwide cohort study involving the Swedish population. *Journal of Thrombosis and Haemostasis*, 15(3), 446–453.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/jth.13614>
- Jonathan C Makielski, MD, F., & L Lee L Eckhardt, MD, F. (2019). *Cardiac excitability, mechanisms of arrhythmia, and action of antiarrhythmic drugs - UpToDate*. Retrieved from https://www.uptodate.com/contents/cardiac-excitability-mechanisms-of-arrhythmia-and-action-of-antiarrhythmic-drugs?search=vaughanwilliams&source=search_result&selectedTitle=1~137&usage_type=default&display_rank=1

- Jürgens, G., Graudal, N. A., & Kampmann, J. P. (2003). Therapeutic drug monitoring of antiarrhythmic drugs. *Clinical Pharmacokinetics*, 42(7), 647–663. <https://doi.org/10.2165/00003088-200342070-00004>
- Katoh, M., Nakajima, M., Yamazaki, H., & Yokoi, T. (2001). Inhibitory effects of CYP3A4 substrates and their metabolites on P-glycoprotein-mediated transport. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 12(4), 505–513. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0928-0987\(00\)00215-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0928-0987(00)00215-3)
- Korantzopoulos, P., Kolettis, T., Siogas, K., & Goudevenos, J. (2003). Atrial fibrillation and electrical remodeling: the potential role of inflammation and oxidative stress. *Medical Science Monitor : International Medical Journal of Experimental and Clinical Research*, 9(9), RA225-9. Retrieved from <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/12960937>
- Laennec, H. D. S., & Mcmichael, J. (1982). *History of atrial fibrillation 1628-1819*. 3(May), 138–141. <https://doi.org/10.1556/IMAS.3.2011.3.14>
- LE HEUZEY, J.-Y., DE FERRARI, G. M., RADZIK, D., SANTINI, M., ZHU, J., & DAVY, J.-M. (2010). A Short-Term, Randomized, Double-Blind, Parallel-Group Study to Evaluate the Efficacy and Safety of Dronedarone versus Amiodarone in Patients with Persistent Atrial Fibrillation: The DIONYSOS Study. *Journal of Cardiovascular Electrophysiology*, 21(6), 597–605. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-8167.2010.01764.x>
- Lei, M., Wu, L., Terrar, D. A., & Huang, C. L. H. (2018). Modernized Classification of Cardiac Antiarrhythmic Drugs. *Circulation*, 138(17), 1879–1896. <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.118.035455>
- Lewis, J. H., Ranard, R. C., Caruso, A., Jackson, L. K., Mullick, F., Ishak, K. G., ... Zimmerman, H. J. (1989). Amiodarone hepatotoxicity: Prevalence and clinicopathologic correlations among 104 patients. *Hepatology*, 9(5), 679–685. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hep.1840090504>
- LYLE A. SIDDOWAY, M. D. (2003). American family physician. *American Family Physician*, 68(11), 2189–2196. Retrieved from <https://www.aafp.org/afp/2003/1201/p2189.html>
- Martino, E., Bartalena, L., Bogazzi, F., & Braverman, L. E. (2001). The Effects of Amiodarone on the Thyroid*. *Endocrine Reviews*, 22(2), 240–254. <https://doi.org/10.1210/edrv.22.2.0427>
- Nademanee, K., Kannan, R., Hendrickson, J., Ookhtens, M., Kay, I., & Singh, B. N. (1984). Amiodarone-digoxin interaction: Clinical significance, time course of development, potential pharmacokinetic mechanisms and therapeutic implications. *Journal of the American College of Cardiology*, 4(1), 111–116. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0735-1097\(84\)80327-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0735-1097(84)80327-7)
- Ohyama, K., Nakajima, M., Suzuki, M., Shimada, N., Yamazaki, H., & Yokoi, T. (2001). Inhibitory effects of amiodarone and its N-deethylated metabolite on human cytochrome P450 activities: Prediction of in vivo drug interactions. *British Journal of Clinical Pharmacology*, 49(3), 244–253. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2125.2000.00134.x>
- Orr, C. F., & Ahlskog, J. E. (2009). Frequency, Characteristics, and Risk Factors for Amiodarone Neurotoxicity. *Archives of Neurology*, 66(7), 865–869. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archneurol.2009.96>

- P. Thornton, D. (2019). *Amiodarone Uses, Dosage & Side Effects - Drugs.com*. Retrieved from <https://www.drugs.com/amiodarone.html>
- Passmann, R. M., & Giardina, E. G. (2019). *Clinical uses of dronedarone - UpToDate*. Retrieved from https://www.uptodate.com/contents/clinical-uses-of-dronedarone?search=dronedarone&source=search_result&selectedTitle=2~51&usage_type=default&display_rank=1
- Perry, J. C., Fenrich, A. L., Hulse, J. E., Triedman, J. K., Friedman, R. A., & Lamberti, J. J. (1996). Pediatric use of intravenous amiodarone: Efficacy and safety in critically ill patients from a multicenter protocol. *Journal of the American College of Cardiology*, 27(5), 1246–1250. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0735-1097\(95\)00591-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0735-1097(95)00591-9)
- Piccini, J. P., & Fauchier, L. (2016). Rhythm control in atrial fibrillation. *The Lancet*, 388(10046), 829–840. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(16\)31277-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(16)31277-6)
- Podrid, P. J., Fuchs, T., & Candinas, R. (1990). Role of the sympathetic nervous system in the genesis of ventricular arrhythmia. *Circulation*, 82(2 Suppl), I103-13. Retrieved from <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/1973640>
- Pozner, Charles N., M. (2019). *Advanced cardiac life support (ACLS) in adults - UpToDate*. Retrieved from https://www.uptodate.com/contents/advanced-cardiac-life-support-acls-in-adults?topicRef=926&source=see_link#H8
- Rosenbaum, M. B., Chiale, P. A., Halpern, M. S., Nau, G. J., Przybylski, J., Levi, R. J., ... Elizari, M. V. (1976). Clinical efficacy of amiodarone as an antiarrhythmic agent. *The American Journal of Cardiology*, 38(7), 934–944. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0002-9149\(76\)90807-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0002-9149(76)90807-9)
- Ross, D. S. (n.d.). Amiodarone and thyroid dysfunction. Retrieved April 5, 2019, from 2018 website: https://www.uptodate.com/contents/amiodarone-and-thyroid-dysfunction?source=bookmarks_widget
- ROTMENSCH, Hesch. H., BELHASSEN, B., SWANSON, B. N., SHOSHANI, D., SPIELMAN, S. R., GREENSPON, A. J., ... HOROWITZ, L. N. (1984). Steady-State Serum Amiodarone Concentrations: Relationships with Antiarrhythmic Efficacy and Toxicity. *Annals of Internal Medicine*, 101(4), 462. <https://doi.org/10.7326/0003-4819-101-4-462>
- Sanoski, C. A., & Bauman, J. L. (2002). Clinical Observations With the Amiodarone/Warfarin Interaction: Dosing Relationships With Long-term Therapy. *Chest*, 121(1), 19–23. <https://doi.org/10.1378/CHEST.121.1.19>
- Saul, J. P., Scott, W. A., Brown, S., Marantz, P., Acevedo, V., Etheridge, S. P., ... Wang, R. (2005). *Intravenous Amiodarone for Incessant Tachyarrhythmias in Children A Randomized, Double-Blind, Antiarrhythmic Drug Trial*. <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.105.534149>
- Schnabel, R. B., Larson, M. G., Yamamoto, J. F., Sullivan, L. M., Pencina, M. J., Meigs, J. B., ... Benjamin, E. J. (2010). Arrhythmia/Electrophysiology Relations of Biomarkers of Distinct Pathophysiological Pathways and Atrial Fibrillation Incidence in the Community. *Circulation*, 121, 200–207. <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.109.882241>

- Shukla, R., Jowett, N. I., Thompson, D. R., & Pohl, J. E. F. (1994). Side effects with amiodarone therapy. *Postgraduate Medical Journal*, 70(825), 492–498. <https://doi.org/10.1136/pgmj.70.825.492>
- Singh, B N, & Vaughan Williams, E. M. (1970). The effect of amiodarone, a new anti-anginal drug, on cardiac muscle. *British Journal of Pharmacology*, 39(4), 657–667. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1476-5381.1970.tb09891.x>
- Singh, Bramah N, & Cingolani, E. (2010). *A New Agent for Atrial Fibrillation: Electrophysiological Properties of Dronedarone*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1074248410377618>
- Sweidan, A. J., Singh, N. K., Dang, N., Lam, V., & Datta, J. (2016). Amiodarone-Induced Pulmonary Toxicity – A Frequently Missed Complication. *Clinical Medicine Insights: Case Reports*, 9, CCRRep.S39809. <https://doi.org/10.4137/CCRRep.S39809>
- Trohman, R. G., Sharma, P. S., McAninch, E. A., & Bianco, A. C. (2018). Amiodarone and the thyroid physiology, pathophysiology, diagnosis and management. *Trends in Cardiovascular Medicine*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tcm.2018.09.005>
- Vander. (2001). Human Physiology: The Mechanism of Body. In *Journal of Helminthology* (Vol. 40). <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022149X00028327>
- Vorperian, V. R., Havighurst, T. C., Miller, S., & January, C. T. (1997). Adverse Effects of Low Dose Amiodarone: A Meta-Analysis. *Journal of the American College of Cardiology*, 30(3), 791–798. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0735-1097\(97\)00220-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0735-1097(97)00220-9)
- WHO Model List of Essential Medicines. (2017). Retrieved from <http://www.who.int/medicines/publications/essentialmedicines/en/>
- Wiersingal, W. M., & Trip2, M. D. (1986). Amiodarone and thyroid hormone metabolism. In *Postgraduate Medical Journal* (Vol. 62). Retrieved from <http://pmj.bmj.com/>
- Zaidel, E. J. (2019). Archives of Clinical and Experimental Cardiology Amiodarone: Updated Review of its Current Usefulness. In *Arc Clin Exp Cardiol* (Vol. 1). Retrieved from www.yumedtext.com
- Zipes, D. P., Prystowsky, E. N., & Heger, J. J. (1984). Amiodarone: Electrophysiologic actions, pharmacokinetics and clinical effects. *Journal of the American College of Cardiology*, 3(4), 1059–1071. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0735-1097\(84\)80367-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0735-1097(84)80367-8)